

General protocol for SLC protein purification

ID: SP000E-3

Authors	¹ David B. Sauer, ¹ Huanyu Li, ¹ Sagar Raturi, ¹ Andreea Scacioc, ¹ Tina Bohstedt, ¹ Abilasha Balakrishnan
Affiliations	¹ Centre for Medicines Discovery, University of Oxford. Oxford, UK

Protocol description

This protocol is used to purify the SLC transporter expressed in Expi293F™ Cells using detergent solubilization followed by a series of different chromatographic methods. Depending on the nature of the expression construct and experimental requirements, the GFP tags can be removed using a proteolytic reaction.

Materials

Biological materials:	
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ HEPES (Apollo Scientific, Catalogue No:BI8181)▪ NaCl (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number S9888)▪ n-Dodecyl-b-D-maltopyranoside (DDM) (Anatrace, Cat# D310)▪ CH210 - Cholesteryl Hemisuccinate Tris Salt (Anatrace, Cat# CH210)▪ cComplete™, EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Roche, Cat# 11873580001)▪ Imidazole (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number 56750-500 G)▪ Magnesium Chloride Hexahydrate (Sigma Aldrich, Catalog number M2670-500G)▪ Adenosine 5-triphosphate disodium salt hydrate, Sigma Aldrich catalog number A2383-10G)▪ TALON® Metal Affinity Resin, (Takara Bio, catalog number 635653)▪ Strep-Tactin®XT 4Flow® high capacity resin (IBA Life Sciences, catalog number 2-5030-025)▪ D(+)-Biotin (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number 851209)▪ TEV (Tobacco Etch Virus) protease (produced in-house)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Dounce homogeniser▪ Gravity flow columns▪ 50 or 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrators▪ 96 well block (2 mL)

Reagents setup

- 1 M HEPES-NaOH pH 7.5
- 2 M MgCl₂
- 2 M imidazole
- 100 mM ATP –NaOH 551.14
- 250 mM D-biotin in base buffer, adjust the pH with NaOH to 7.5 and store at -20 °C.
- Base buffer (50 mM HEPES-NaOH pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl)
- SEC buffer (20 mM HEPES-NaOH pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 2 CMC DDM/CHS)
- TALON wash buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 10 mM Imidazole, 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM ATP, 3 CMC DDM/CHS)

- TALON elution buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 300 mM Imidazole, 3 times the critical micelle concentration DDM/CHS)
- Strep wash buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 3 CMC DDM/CHS)
- Strep elution buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 50 mM Biotin, 3 CMC DDM/CHS)
- SEC buffer (20 mM HEPES-NaOH pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 2 CMC DDM/CHS), filtered through 0.22 μ M membrane
- 10% (w/v) DDM/CHS (leave at 4 °C overnight to allow complete solubilisation and store at -20 °C)

Procedure

Day 1

1. Thaw the frozen cell pellet in a water bath set to room temperature.
2. Prepare 150 mL of solubilization buffer containing 1% DDM/CHS by adding 15 mL of 10% (w/v) DDM/CHS and one Protease Inhibitor Cocktail tablet per 50mL. Make the volume up to 150 mL with the base buffer. Allow the tablets to dissolve.
3. Suspend thawed pellets with solubilization buffer and pour into a dounce homogeniser, homogenise the solution by pulling and pushing the plunger up and down approximately 20 times. Keep on ice.
4. Rotate the container slowly for 1 hour at 4 °C.
5. Centrifuge the solution at 50,000 x g for 30 min at 4 °C.
6. Equilibrate 4-6 mL bed volume of TALON resin with the base buffer.
7. Collect the supernatant and add equilibrated TALON resin to the supernatant, rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
8. Transfer the solution to a gravity flow column, allow the solution to flow through.
9. Wash the resin with 10 times the bed volume of TALON wash buffer.
10. Perform elution with 5 times the bed volume of TALON elution buffer.
11. Equilibrate 4-6 mL bed volume of strep XT resin with TALON elution buffer.
12. Add equilibrated strep XT resin to the eluted solution, put on a rotator and rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
13. Pour the solution into an empty gravity flow column, allow the solution to flow through.
14. Wash the resin with 10 times the bed volume of strep wash buffer.
15. Elute with 3-4 incubations in 3-5 mL of strep elution buffer for 15-20 minutes between each elution.
16. Measure protein concentration using a nanodrop and add TEV to the protein solution in the ratio of 1:5 (w/w) to 1:10 (w/w), respectively.
17. Slowly rotate the container overnight at 4 °C.

Day 2

18. In a gravity flow column, equilibrate 2-4 mL bed volume of TALON resin with SEC buffer.
19. Add equilibrated TALON resin to the overnight TEV reaction mixture and rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
20. Using an empty gravity flow column let the solution collect flow through solution in a 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal filter.
21. Concentrate the solution by centrifuging at 3,000 g at 4 °C, stop and gently agitate every 5 minutes.

22. Equilibrate a Superdex® 200 Increase 10/300 GL column using SEC buffer.
23. Concentrate the sample down to the desired injection volume and inject the sample into the sample loop.
24. Run a SEC elution.
25. Pool peak fractions in a fresh 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrator and concentrate to the required volume/concentration 3,000 g at 4 °C.

Additional notes

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.